

STRATEGIES FOR IMPLEMENTING SELECTED BIOLOGY-RELATED DISCIPLINES' CURRICULA IN THE POST-COVID-19 PANDEMIC ERA: A CASE STUDY OF OSUN STATE UNIVERSITIES

BY

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ABSTRACT

Coronavirus pandemic affected the educational system worldwide such that schools, colleges, and universities are totally shutdown as a measure to control the spread of the virus resulting in difficulties for students, teachers, and parents. This brought the need for open and distance learning to the front burner. This study aims to identify the strategies used in implementing selected Biology-related disciplines' curricula during the COVID-19 in the study area. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with the population of the study consisting of lecturers and students in private and public universities in Osun State. The sample comprised 45 lecturers across the selected universities in the study area. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used for this study. One Federal, one state and one private university were selected using simple random sampling technique. From each of the selected universities, three Biology-related departments were randomly selected. Five lecturers were selected from each department, fifteen from each university making a total of 45 lecturers. The research instruments used for data collection for this study was Checklist for Curriculum Implementation Strategies (CCIS). The findings revealed diverse strategies including; Online strategy, blended strategy, face-to face strategy and no strategy used.

Keywords: Strategy, Implementing, Biology-related Disciplines, Curricula, Post-pandemic era, Case study, Nigeria Universities, Education Policy

INTRODUCTION

In the year 2020, Nigeria and other nations of the world saw the interruption to the education system due to the coronavirus which started in Wuhan, China in 2019. All schools in the country were closed as a precautionary measure to limit the spread of this dreaded disease for a period of seven months (march to September,2020) in Nigeria. The COVID-19 pandemic was a massive challenge for the entire world, resulting in radical transformation across many areas of life, including education.

The education system has not fully recovered from the series of unfortunate events triggered by this pandemic. Science education suffered setback as many researchers could not have access to their research institutions and learning of science became more impossible. This led to many schools and institution seeking alternative to classroom education and sought for other possible means to deliver education without getting into the four walls of a classroom. One of the main science subjects offered in senior secondary schools in Nigeria is

Biology which is essential in preparing students for careers in fields like medical, nursing, pharmacy, forestry, fishery, and other related fields. Furthermore, because Biology is so fascinating and closely related to the study of natural occurrences, it continues to be the subject of choice for a lot of students.

The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008), indicated that the goals delineated for the Biology curriculum of secondary schools in Nigeria comprise of multiple facets: the enhancement of proficient laboratory and field skills in Biology; the procurement of significant and useful knowledge in Biology; the capacity to utilise scientific knowledge in everyday life with respect to agriculture, personal health, and community health; and the development of a logical and practical skill as the study of life or living things is the focus of several biological disciplines. Using these fields in the classroom is important because it can lead to a better understanding of complex pathogen-host interactions by leveraging advances in computational Biology and molecular Biology (Aderemi, et al 2011). Scientists across the world have been working on topics related to the present pandemic with public health becoming a relevant and urgent field that demands action to improve healthcare systems and get ready for pandemics in the future. Many fields within the field of Biology, such as medicine and surgery, pharmacy, microbiological science, immunological research, the genetic make-up of man, Epidemiology, Nursing science, Zoology, Botany, Anatomy, Physiology, Public health, Biology education, Biochemistry, Medical rehabilitation, Dentistry, Biotechnology, and more, provide research perspectives that are ideal for monitoring, assessing, comprehending, and interpreting the effects of epidemics, deepening the need for interdisciplinary collaboration (Georgie, OleaMarc, SerreHwa-Lung, 2005)

Rogan and Grayson's (2003) paradigm for curricular implementation sets the tune for this study. They emphasized that three main constructs make up the framework: an implementation profile, innovative capacity, and external assistance or influence. These three conceptions are useful instruments for understanding, assessing, and communicating the extent to which curriculum principles—especially when it comes to science education can be effectively implemented. The 'External Influence' component consists of five sub-constructs: providing learners with direct assistance as well as the tools they need for creativity, professional development, managing different kinds of change pressures, monitoring techniques, and resilience-enhancing support systems. When faced with inadequate resources and inadequate support, including professional development, teachers could oppose the implementation of the new curriculum and continue to teach using their old framework.

Figure 1 describes the three main factors that influence how a curriculum is Implemented:

Outside influence, capacity to innovate, and profile of implementation. The outside influence

refers to the factors outside the school or organization that can influence how a curriculum is

Implemented. This could include things like government policies, community attitudes, and

Therefore, the capacity to Innovate refers to the ability of the schools or organization to make changes and adapt the curriculum to meet the needs of the students. This last factor is the profile of implementation could include things like funding, leadership, and teacher training. The last factor is the profile of implementation which refers to the characteristics of the school or

Organization that can affect how the curriculum is implemented. This could include school

Culture, the student population, and the resources available.

As opined by Brown & Rodgers, (2002), when lecturers introduce new material, their sense of self-efficacy and self-esteem are undermined by feelings of doubt, tension, and inadequacy, which leads to distantiation) According to Suchman (2003), instructors' perceptions and interpretations of the implementation of new curricula are greatly influenced by their physical and cultural surroundings. A hostile learning environment, characterized by a dearth of necessary resources could be a powerful inducer of distancing. On the other hand, catalysts for change, such as the effects of COVID-19, can be transformative forces. The second construct, 'Capacity to Innovate,' is composed of four sub-constructs: school

ethos and administration, student attributes, teacher attributes, and physical resources. Dofing (2021) observes differences in instructors' reactions when a new curriculum is being implemented. According to Spillane (2020), a lecturer's ability to impact change in the curriculum is closely related to a number of factors, including their background knowledge, level of experience, and expertise as well as the resources that are available, the types of students they teach, and the management team's support. The last construct, 'Profile of Implementation,' is made up of four sub-constructs: the nature and application of science practical work, the dynamics of classroom interaction, evaluation techniques, and the integration of science in society.

Figure 1: Framework of Curriculum Implementation (Adopted by Adeleke (2023))

According to Mafugu (2021), increasing the learning process requires the use of both interactions and assessment. There are four levels within each sub-construct; level one represents teacher-centered techniques, while level four represents sophisticated learner-centered practices. These levels provide a range of strategies

that can be used in a classroom; the best option depends on the particular circumstance. For example, the teacher-centered approach might work best in situations where class sizes are large. This study the first of its type at the Faculty of Agriculture, Environment, and Natural Resources Management—looks

into how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the way curricula is implemented. In order to address a topic that has never been studied before, this study will examine the unique experiences lecturers had when putting the curriculum into practice during the COVID-19 pandemic (Rogan & Grayson, 2003). Even while lecturers have a great deal of expertise implementing curricula, a significant portion of their knowledge is not documented, which leaves a gap in academic understanding. The results of this study could lead to a faculty reassessment of how the curriculum is implemented, and they might even have wider implications for the university as a whole. In addition, the study may provide academic staff with insightful information by emphasizing steps that are required to reach desired goals. Faculty members rarely share their experiences with one another, and this has gone unnoticed for a long time.

Most importantly, the study's final conclusions might help with the nation's economic problems. The young students of today have the necessary knowledge and abilities, and they could be able to address some economic problems in an efficient manner, especially in the agriculture sector, which is the backbone of the Nigerian economy. Among the most important questions is: How did instructors cope during the COVID-19 pandemic while implementing a new curriculum? Rogan and Grayson (2003) Theory of Curriculum Implementation, which centers on three essential constructs—the implementation profile, the ability to innovate, and Outside Support Agencies—formed the framework for the investigation. According to Rogan and Aldous (2005), the implementation profile is a useful instrument for comprehending, evaluating, and communicating the degree to which a reform program's goals are met. It essentially acts as a blueprint for the educational environment, giving curriculum planners the ability to see

different implementation stages of the curriculum and identify process flaws. When implementing, this framework makes it easier to identify best practices. When it involves school-related variables that could help or hinder the adoption of creative curriculum ideas, Rogan and Grayson (2003) emphasize how important they are to the process.

NATIONAL UNIVERSITIES COMMISSION

In Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Education oversees the National Universities Commission (NUC), a government organization founded in 1962, with the responsibility of supervising the growth and administration of higher education in the nation. The Commission's primary responsibilities include approving all university academic programmes in Nigeria, authorising the founding of postsecondary educational institutions that offer degree programmes, and guaranteeing programme quality through regular university accreditation. At the moment, federal, state, and private universities' academic programmes are governed by the NUC throughout Nigeria. The National Universities Commission (NUC) oversees the creation of new facilities and postgraduate units at universities, advises the federal government on the basic needs of universities, and advises on university establishment and location. Furthermore, according to NEEDS (2014) and Lassa (1992), the NUC is also in charge of creating and enforcing minimum academic standards, registering degrees and other academic programmes granted by universities, and creating periodic plans regarding the general programmes that staff members of federal universities will pursue.

The National Universities Commission (NUC) in (2007) came out with a document containing all programmes that are offering in the Nigerian Universities.

The BMAS documents were produced for the under listed academic disciplines:

- i) Administration; Management and Management Technology;
- ii) Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries and Home Economics;
- iii) Arts;
- iv) Basic Medical and Health Science
- v) Education;
- vi) Engineering and Technology;
- vii) Environmental Sciences;
- viii) Law;
- ix) Pharmaceutical Sciences
- x) Medicine and Dentistry;
- xi) Science;
- xii) Social Sciences;
- xiii) Veterinary Medicine.

Higher education institutions in Nigeria have faced a number of difficulties recently with their science programmes, from poor administration to insufficient supervision. Nigerian universities offer a variety of programmes, including education, which covers the social sciences, arts, and sciences. There are core courses that students must take in order to graduate from education programmes. Core courses like Curriculum and Instruction I and II are mandatory for all students to complete in order to graduate. Not only is Curriculum and Instruction a required course, but some universities also offer master's and doctoral programmes in it. Like many other programmes in Nigerian higher education institutions, curriculum and instruction face a number of difficulties.

CONCEPT OF CURRICULUM STUDIES

According to Ali & Ajibola, (2015), a curriculum is the set of courses and their materials that are offered at a college or university. It comes from a more comprehensive syllabus that specifies the subjects to be understood and the degree of comprehension needed to achieve a particular grade or standard, it is by nature prescriptive. As opined by Kelly (2008), "Curriculum encompasses all the learning

that is intentionally planned and guided by the school, whether conducted in groups or individually, within or outside the school premises." Put more simply, the curriculum specifies ahead of time the learning goals to be met and the approaches to take in order to reach them.

In the opinion of Offorma (2005), curriculum consists of three main parts: the programme of studies, the programme of activities, and the programme of guidance. Curriculum is an organised learning experience that students receive in a school setting. As a result, the idea of curriculum has changed to accommodate the various educational requirements found in different academic disciplines. Thus, a Curriculum is defined as a set of subjects and/or knowledge content by Blenkin (2012).

It is essentially the process by which learners are taught knowledge and skills using the most effective techniques available. It acts as a well-organized course outline, outlining the goals and educational opportunities required to reach them. More generally, it is a way of getting people ready to be useful members of their community and productive citizens. As a result, curriculum serves as a teaching tool intended to support students' overall development as well as to instruct them. Akinsola and Abe (2006) asserted that the curriculum includes all of the information and experiences that a child learns both inside and outside of the classroom, whether they are planned into a schedule or happen outside of it. It thus basically refers to all of the experiences that the learner has, regardless of when or how they happen.

According to Jeffs and Smith (2010), the idea of curriculum acts as a key distinction between formal and informal education. They admit that some non-formal educators have incorporated curriculum theory and practice into their attempts to make content more understandable, noting that curriculum

approaches that prioritize goals and comprehensive programmes, appear to support students' overall development. This study therefore approached curriculum as the entirety of knowledge intended to be imparted to students by lecturers in and outside the educational setting, with the aim of achieving specific objectives. It does this by taking account of the different viewpoints of various scholars on the concept of curriculum. Considering the research that has been done so far on the concept of curriculum, it is essential to look into the problems related to curriculum in Nigerian universities.

Furthermore, a curriculum, according to Okudishu (2013), is a collection of teaching strategies, educational opportunities, and performance evaluations of students that are meant to elicit and assess the intended learning outcomes of a specific course. It functions as a thorough lesson plan that is determined by policymakers and is made up of a variety of materials arranged into courses and disciplines with the general goal of accomplishing particular learning goals. From the perspective of education, it refers to the order of experiences and activities that students must participate in, in order to develop the life skills and personal potential that they will need as adults. Curriculum programmes are thus, foundational courses that are offered at all educational levels, including colleges of education, and at the undergraduate level. Certain universities in Nigeria also offer the curriculum as a stand-alone programme at the master's and doctoral levels. Curriculum and Instruction (I) is the main focus of the first semester, while Curriculum and Instruction (II) is covered in the second semester of an undergraduate curriculum programme. These classes are made to fit into the particular specialization programme. For example, the curriculum of science education programmes is adapted to fit the needs of science-related disciplines,

whereas the curriculum of art and social science education programmes is similarly modified. The curriculum program's main goals are to acquaint students with the basic ideas behind curriculum development, which include learning opportunities, content, goals, and assessment techniques. The programme also attempts to provide students with the information and abilities required for developing curricula and to enable critical evaluation of curricula in terms of their applicability to national objectives. To ensure successful teaching and learning outcomes, there must be a strong connection between curriculum and instruction. This relationship can be seen in a number of areas, including the definition of the objective, the choice of learning activities, the learning resources, the teaching strategies, the media used for instruction, and evaluation.

Curriculum lays out the main goals of a course or programme, including the knowledge and skills that students should be able to acquire. To guarantee that teaching activities are concentrated on achieving the desired learning outcomes, instructional practices should be closely aligned with these objectives.

- **Learning Experience Selection:** The curriculum establishes the kinds of learning activities that students will take part in in order to meet the predetermined goals. A range of activities, including talks, debates, practical exercises, and projects, should be included in instruction. These activities should be selected to help students grasp and become proficient in the material.
- **Resources and Learning Materials:** The curriculum lists the tools and materials required to support instruction. Textbooks, articles, multimedia materials, lab supplies, and internet resources are a few examples of these. Carefully chosen instructional materials can improve

student learning and accommodate a variety of learning preferences.

- **Instructional Methods and Media:** The curriculum offers recommendations for the instructional methods and media that can be used. Experiential learning opportunities, group projects, lectures, and demonstrations are a few examples of instructional methods. Depending on the needs of the students and the subject matter, instructional media can range from traditional classroom materials to digital technologies.
- **Evaluation:** The curriculum lays out the parameters and requirements for assessing what students have learned. These standards should be followed when evaluating instruction in order to track students' development and attainment of learning goals. Tests, quizzes, projects, presentations, and portfolios are examples of evaluation techniques.

Nigerian experience with curriculum innovation includes constant efforts to update and revise curricula to meet the evolving needs of society and technological and knowledge advancements. To discover new trends and best practices in a subject area, educators, legislators, business leaders, and other stakeholders frequently collaborate on curriculum innovation projects. Initiatives to innovate curricula in Nigeria might centre on incorporating interdisciplinary perspectives, incorporating new technologies, updating content to reflect recent research and developments, and encouraging active and experiential learning methods. By preparing students for the opportunities and challenges of the future, these innovations hope to improve the calibre and relevance of education.

The curriculum programme aims to provide graduates with essential competencies and proficiencies to:

1. Recognise concepts from the curriculum in relation to their field of expertise.

2. Determine which models are relevant to the actual state of education in their nation.
3. Give instruction in the curricular principles and how to apply them to the particular degree type—single, joint, or combined—that is involved.
4. Encourage intellectual curiosity in students by having them study the curriculum and helping them understand how relevant it is in different situations and how it can be applied to a variety of issues.
5. Establish a solid foundation of understanding regarding the operation of national education policies and cultivate the necessary competencies to make effective use of that knowledge in various contexts.
6. Encourage students to apply their newly acquired knowledge, skills, and analytical tools to the resolution of curricular issues in society.

The program's curriculum seeks to:

1. Give students the analytical tools they need to address challenges related to curriculum policy.
2. Students can acquire a variety of transferable skills that are useful in the planning, development, implementation, and assessment of curricula by studying curriculum.
3. Give pupils the capacity to create streamlined frameworks and to think analytically in order to study the real world.
4. Provide students with the foundational knowledge and skills necessary to pursue advanced coursework in curriculum, related fields, or interdisciplinary curriculum-related fields.

CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION

A curriculum outlines the goals and the procedures for reaching them (Kelly, 2018). A curriculum, according to

Offorma (2015), consists of three components: a study plan, an activity plan, and guidance. According to Blenkin (2017), the curriculum includes subjects and content that teach students the most efficient ways to acquire knowledge and skills. The curriculum acts as a spur for social development and transformation. Biggs and Tang (2015) asserted that the curriculum needs to achieve its stated goals. It is recommended to use constructive alignment, an outcomes-based strategy based on constructivist and curriculum theories. According to Biggs and Tang (2015), constructivist theory views students as unique individuals who can actively construct their knowledge through various activities. According to curriculum theory, when instruction and evaluation activities match learning objectives, learning takes place as best it can (Biggs & Tang, 2015). According to Onyeachu (2018), implementation is the key to a curriculum's critical evaluation even with proper preparation and documentation indicating that implementation is a difficult component of the curriculum and a crucial element of effective innovation. Aydin, (2017) highlighted how difficult it is to apply curricula in schools, especially in light of newly developing technology while Babalola, (2019) affirmed that curriculum implementation is still a recurring problem in education, frequently leading to a discrepancy between intended and actual execution describing it as the difficult process of turning a difficult curricular concept—which is usually provided as a design or plan—into workable, applicable steps that can be taken in a teaching-learning setting. A well-written and well-meaning theoretical concept must be translated into a workable practical solution through implementation. Several scholars have thoroughly examined the idea of curricular implementation, each providing unique insights (Ivowi, 2014; Onyeachu, 2018). Various academics have offered varying

accounts of how curricula are implemented.

Ivowi (2014) defined curriculum implementation as the distribution of an organized set of learning activities, the supply of tools to carry out the plan efficiently, and the actual plan execution in the classroom, which promotes teacher-student interactions. Curriculum implementation, according to Mkpa and Izuagba (2019), entails the learner—for whom the program is intended—interacting with the contents and materials in order to acquire the skills, attitudes, and abilities that are required. The curriculum implementation process is the phase in which students, under the direction of an instructor, participates in educational activities to optimize learning, which is reflected in the student's altered behavior or perspective on problems. According to Onyeachu (2008), it is the process of converting all prepared curricular materials into useful applications in the classroom. This entails the joint efforts of educators, students, parents, and school administrators as well as interactions with the physical space, educational resources, and social and psychological environments.

Though Okebukola (2005), averred that curriculum encompasses teaching through verbal and nonverbal exposition, hands-on activities in laboratories, workshops, and the discipline, student-student and student-material conversations, assessment and feedback as the intermediate steps in curriculum implementation, curricula are faced with barriers that hinder the successful implementation of the curriculum. Curriculum developers, adopters, and implementers should be mindful of detractors such as these and address them adequately to minimize the impediments to curriculum implementation in learning institutions as curriculum implementations are faced with barriers, such as a lack of content and pedagogical knowledge, which hinder the successful implementation. It is

therefore important for curriculum developers, adopters, and implementers to be aware of possible obstacles and critics. If educational institutions want to reduce obstacles to curriculum implementation, they must be ready to handle these difficulties effectively.

STRATEGIES USED FOR IMPLEMENTING CURRICULUM

After a curriculum is developed, it is expected that a commensurate dedication to its efficient execution will follow. In order for the curriculum to effectively meet the demands of students and society in a world that is always changing, effective plans for its quick implementation must be put in place. As reported by Jon and Joseph, (2007) lack of administrative knowledge and abilities on the side of educators have resulted in poor implementation of over 90% of new curriculum. A complete revamp is therefore required before a curriculum can be effectively implemented in Nigeria. This includes modifying one's own routines, behaviors, program focus, learning environments, and scheduling (Leslie, 1976). It is critical to understand that the quality of the original planning and the meticulousness with which the phases of curriculum development have been carried out have an impact on teachers' willingness to adopt new curricula in Nigeria (Michael et al., 2006). Teachers must have a thorough awareness of the customs, power structures, and self-perceptions of students within the school (Seymour, 1990).

Successful curriculum implementers understand that learners need to be attracted to the curriculum not just intellectually but also emotionally and morally. Remarkably, moral factors drive a lot of instructors' actions (Pullan & Crevola, 2023). Also, planning is essential for a successful curriculum implementation, with a focus on people, programs, and processes. When a new

curriculum is implemented, teachers must change some of their routines and viewpoints.

According to Michael, (2007) some school districts experience program implementation failure when they ignore the human component and devote their time and resources to solely changing the program or procedure. He emphasized that it is crucial to concentrate on the new program in order to give people creative ways to fulfill the goals of the school's initiatives. In this framework, organizational programs are equally important as recognizing departments may help people go in the path needed for an implementation to be effective (Michael, 2007).

Therefore, the following are essential for the effective implementation of curricula:

Support

Curriculum designers should provide crucial support for any suggested innovations or curriculum revisions in order to ensure successful implementation. It is the responsibility of the entire school, including the curriculum creators, to develop capability. What teachers and students bring to the instructional core in terms of resources, knowledge, and skills is referred to as capacity or capability. It also encompasses the skillful efforts of the entire school administration with the goal of enhancing and optimizing the curriculum's implementation and teacher and student participation. Sustaining the curriculum and providing continuous maintenance and assistance are essential to improving students' learning results. Building a team of skilled implementers requires ongoing assistance from the school system (Michael, 2007).

Communication

A curriculum specialist needs to be aware of the communication channels inside a school (or school system) in order to guarantee effectiveness. These channels

can be horizontal (involving people at the same level of the hierarchy) or vertical (involving people at different levels of the school hierarchy). For example, communication between two teachers is horizontal, whereas communication between a principal and a teacher is vertical. Peer-to-peer horizontal networking is promoted in several school restructuring programs. It is thought that when people see themselves as equals and are equally involved in changing the curriculum, communication would be easier. Effective horizontal communication is assumed in many curriculum activities that combine subjects or integrate significant curriculum components. In schools, there could be official avenues for horizontal communication, but most of it is informal. In order to establish cohesive school communities comprising educators, administrators, students, and community members, effective curriculum leaders aggressively support a range of communication channels (Valerie et al., 2004). In order to achieve effective communication, formal and informal collaboration must be coordinated in a delicate way (Andy & Michael, 2012).

Incrementalism

A lot of people think of implementation as a method of managing change. The people in charge of execution ought to raise concerns regarding the underlying objectives of the proposed modification. Change management is aided by focusing just on curriculum and school culture modifications. A new curriculum or even a new textbook series may only be considered successful if all of the teachers are actively using the educational program or resources.

However, the crucial query at every stage of curriculum creation and execution is: What benefit will the change have for teachers and students alike? Richard (2007) said. Even though it's thought of as

a process of transformation, common queries are as follows:

- Does the modification make sense and have a purpose?
- Will it improve students' learning and the pedagogical and curriculum practices of teachers?

Improvement is expected to follow change, and it takes time to improve teacher effectiveness and student learning (Richard, 2007).

STRATEGIES USED IN IMPLEMENTING THE CURRICULA OF BIOLOGY-RELATED DISCIPLINES

The 21st century has witnessed a revolutionary change in education, with technology playing a key part. The old ways of teaching, in which teachers were viewed mainly as information providers, have changed. The use of technology has resulted in a redefinition of the responsibilities of educators, positioning them as mentors, motivators, and facilitators who foster dynamic learning environments and enthusiastic student engagement (Onyema & Deborah, 2018). Numerous learning styles, including blended, virtual, remote, mobile, distributed, machine, ubiquitous, deep, cooperative, and collaborative learning, have been made possible by technology through the years. Nearly every facet of the learning process is moving to an online format as education embraces digitalization. Students and other education stakeholders face difficulties navigating the intricacies of online learning as a result of this change. Using the right educational technology makes it easier to access materials, such as Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), and offers a variety of learning styles to meet the needs of a wide range of students (Onyema, 2018). The idea of online education entails using digital platforms and tools to provide instruction in a virtual setting.

A number of variables, including dependable internet connections, capable learning applications, digital literacy, and the availability and accessibility of technology, affect how effective online education is. Online learning environments and inclusive education are greatly aided by these platforms. Online education effectively distributes lectures, virtual classroom sessions, and instructional materials via the internet. It is rooted in distance education and driven by the emergence of digital technologies (Onlineeducation.com, 2020). Taking advantage of online education platforms can help reduce educational gaps and lower the global prevalence of illiteracy, as mobile and internet technology are widely used internationally. A vast selection of online learning resources and platforms are essential for enabling distance learning, particularly in times of emergency like the coronavirus epidemic.

Some of these technology tools/platforms are listed below:

1. GoToMeeting.com
2. Skype.com
3. Google Classroom/Open Online education (edu.google.com)
4. Youtube.com
5. Blackboard.com
6. udemy.com
7. coursera.org
8. memory.com
9. alison.com
10. edx.org
11. easyclass.com
12. vedamo.com
13. Khanacademy.org
14. TED-Ed (ed.ted.com)
15. Codeacademy.com
16. Stanford Online (Online.stanford.edu)
17. futurelearn.com
18. rcampus.com
19. learnopia.com
20. Peer 2 Peer University (p2pu.org)
21. Teachers pay Teachers (teacherspayteachers.com)
22. Thinkific (thinkific.com)
23. MOOC.org
24. openculture.com
25. academicearth.org
26. itunes U Free courses (apps.apple.com)
27. lessonpaths.com
28. memrise.com
29. funbrain.com (for kids)
30. whyville.net (for teens)
31. Edmodo (edmodo.com)
32. schoology (schoology.com)
33. classdojo (classdojo.com)
34. google hangouts (hangouts.google.com)
35. Zoom (zoom.us)
36. Whatsapp.com

Online learning is made possible by the use of educational technologies, which also helps to build connections, relationships, and exchanges between students and teachers. Through the facilitation of content development, course sharing, evaluations, and feedback, it improves the quality of teaching and learning experiences overall. Teachers can interact with their pupils without difficulty from any place, giving them the freedom to arrange lectures whenever it is most convenient for both of them. These tools are useful add-ons to traditional classroom instruction, enabling teachers and students to improve their digital literacy in line with new trends in education. Additionally, being tech-savvy increases students' and teachers' enthusiasm, competence, confidence, creativity, employability, and overall productivity while preparing them for the challenges of the future.

Millions of students are now forced to continue their studies and learn from home due to the coronavirus outbreak. The home has long been the center of informal education, despite the fact that this change may appear recent. According to Education Task (2020), a considerable proportion of college students say they would rather study in the convenience of their own homes, so learning from home is becoming more and more commonplace. This preference stems from the ease of access to all required resources, which removes the need to venture outside of

one's study area. However, many teachers, students, and parents find it difficult to make the switch to formal education in a home environment, especially in developing nations where access to, and use of, technology in the classroom is not always universal.

Apart from the cost consequences of online learning, there are also other elements that may hinder effective at-home education. The difficulties of studying from home are increased by obstacles including unstable power supplies, network problems, possible distractions, low digital proficiency, problems with accessibility and availability, and the requirement to become acquainted with new technology. The problems are further exacerbated by noises coming from the neighborhood and from within. Extended school closures have the potential to deny millions of students—especially those in third-world countries, rural areas, and persons with special needs—access to education. Unequal access to technology is becoming a major concern, especially in many countries. Acknowledging these difficulties, UNESCO launched programs to support teachers and students in impacted nations by providing free software to enable home-based remote learning. According to Catherine (2020), in order to lessen the effects of school closures brought on by the coronavirus, UNESCO created an online guide with connections to apps for remote learning and other resources. It was anticipated that pupils would use the mandatory school closures brought on by the coronavirus to improve their proficiency with digital learning and develop productive study habits at home. Notwithstanding the difficulties brought about by the epidemic, students were urged to see this time as a chance to improve their ability to solve problems and gain proficiency with digital tools.

Oyelekan and Oloyede (2020) carried out research in Ilorin, Nigeria, with an

emphasis on how science instructors in the senior high school level used creative teaching techniques. Students' performance in science disciplines is still below average in Nigerian secondary schools, despite significant attempts to improve science teaching. When used properly, a variety of cutting-edge teaching techniques created by educators have shown to have a major positive impact on students' academic achievement.

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to find out how much scientific instructors in Ilorin, Nigeria, use cutting-edge teaching techniques when instructing senior high school science students. Using a stratified random sampling technique, 256 science instructors were chosen from secondary schools in the Ilorin East, South, and West Local Government Areas to be part of the research sample.

The Innovative Teaching Strategies Questionnaire (ITSQ), a researcher-designed questionnaire with a high reliability rating of 0.91 Cronbach alpha, was used to gather the study's data. The results showed that most scientific teachers regularly used only two (2) of the thirty-six (36) creative teaching strategies that were chosen, while the remaining strategies were only occasionally used. Furthermore, the findings showed that, among scientific instructors, there was no discernible variation in the application of creative teaching techniques according to experience and credentials. Among other things, the authors recommended that science instructors take advantage of the chances presented by these creative approaches to improve their students' academic performance.

Nwosu (2014) asserts that a sizable portion of scientific instructors are deficient in the fundamental skills needed for activity-based learning. As a result, the traditional talk and chalk (lecture) approach has remained the most popular teaching strategy. Ajaja (2018) went on to say that a decrease in interest in science is

a result of the teaching and learning strategies used in science education. Alternative teaching methods that can engage pupils and improve their academic performance are therefore clearly needed. The realization that different subjects must be taught and that different talents are meant to be developed leads to the adoption of a variety of creative teaching techniques.

A crucial component acknowledged for its significance, educators have developed a plethora of creative ways to actively involve students in the teaching and learning process (Slavin, 2019). In order for instructors to successfully incorporate these tactics into the classroom, they must not only be familiar with them but also develop the abilities required for them to be used in an educational setting. A teacher who is not familiar with a variety of tactics will not only not try to use them, but also find it difficult to use them successfully. Empirical research conducted recently has shown that some creative approaches produce better learning outcomes for children. For instance, a study by Lamidi, Oyelekan, and Olorundare (2015) examined how the mastery learning instructional strategy affected secondary school students' performance in the difficult subject of the mole concept, which has been shown to be difficult for learners to understand. According to the study, students who received instruction using the mastery learning technique performed noticeably better than those in the control group. Similarly, the impact of computer-assisted instruction using Student Team Successful Completion Division (STAD) and Learning Together Model (LTM) methods of cooperation was investigated in relation to the physics achievement and drive of Nigerian secondary students in a study conducted by Gambari, Yusuf, and Thomas (2015). The results showed that pupils receiving individualized computer instruction (ICI) performed worse than those receiving STAD and LTM

instruction. Furthermore, gender-friendly cooperative learning mechanisms were found. In a more recent study, gender and test scores were taken into account as moderating variables as Abdulwahab, Oyelekan, and Olorundare (2016) investigated the effects of a cooperative teaching approach on the academic accomplishment of senior secondary school students in electrochemistry. The findings of this study also showed that students who were taught the cooperative instructional technique performed better than students in the control group, with the low scores benefiting from the strategy the most.

Thus, evaluating the degree to which educators are using creative approaches is essential in tackling the problem of students' poor performance in the sciences. The suggested method for putting the biology curriculum in senior secondary schools into practice emphasizes the value of field research, supervised learning, laboratory methods and skills, and conceptual thinking. Models, demonstrations, field visits, conversations, group work, project work, and enlisting the help of resources are more techniques. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2009) outlined the curriculum's objectives, substance, and context, and these approaches are mandated to meet those needs. The chemistry curriculum emphasizes hands-on learning and prioritizes resources that are readily available in the area. The suggested approaches include lab work, field visits, guided discovery, class discussions, and demonstrations (NERDC, 2009). The curriculum uses a spiral structure to arrange the physics content, and it strongly recommends the guided discovery teaching technique in order to achieve the program's goals. The senior secondary school physics curriculum's recommended implementation strategies highlight the value of experimentation, inquiry,

discussion, and problem-solving (NERDC, 2009c). The goal of successfully implementing this curriculum is to enable students to thrive in a variety of subject areas and realize their full potential.

Science instructors are required by the current curriculum to teach a certain amount of material during certain weeks, terms, and times of the school year. The difficulty for educators, though, frequently comes in how to impart the necessary knowledge to the students. This difficulty could be from having to cover a lot of ground in a short amount of time, not having the required materials on hand, or not being experienced with efficient teaching techniques. Furthermore, studies indicate that some teaching pedagogies may be more beneficial than others, and that a strategy's efficacy is frequently dependent on the concept, subject, or issue being taught (Barbosa, Jofili & Watta, 2014; Longjohn, 2019; Umoren & Ogong, 2020). It is therefore essential to adopt and apply one or more cutting-edge solutions that are specifically suited to a given science topic or material.

In order to ensure that lessons are delivered in the classroom effectively, educational credentials are essential. Professional development is no longer only a one-time event held on a designated day of the year; instead, it needs to be a part of educators' everyday work lives. According to Okunloye (2019), obtaining specialized knowledge from teacher training institutions, such as universities and colleges of education, is necessary for successful and effective teaching as a vocation. Recognizing that classroom instructors are the cornerstone of institutional education is crucial. Through regular in-service training and continued practice, teachers must transform from being simply educators to becoming educators. Expanding on this, Omosewo (2018) says that improving pupils' performance in physics requires teachers to have a strong academic

background. According to Khurshid and Zahur (2013), instructors with higher levels of professional qualification knew more about cutting-edge teaching techniques than teachers with lower levels of qualification.

Certification in pedagogy and subject area has become increasingly necessary as a result of the need for highly qualified teachers. But merely basing teacher quality on credentials hasn't produced the desired results. Throughout the process of imparting knowledge and fostering cognitive development, teachers have a tremendous impact on their students. Because of this, teachers should act in a way that is consistent with positive behavior, speech, and attitudes because children will probably follow their lead. Fullan (2015) argues that in the context of educational reform, professional development for teachers should effectively handle the multifaceted issues of putting educational standards into practice, collaborating with a diverse student body, and adjusting to changing student assessment methods. It is impossible to overstate the importance of professional development in the context of successful reforming the education system.

It serves as a bridge that takes aspiring and experienced teachers from where they are now to the place, they need to be in order to successfully take on the new challenges of assisting all students in reaching better standards of learning and development. Instructors must to have a strong background in the subjects they teach as well as expertise in pedagogy and learning theories. In the context of teaching and learning, teaching experience is highly significant. Experience includes the mindset, abilities, or information that a teacher has picked up via involvement in educational initiatives. The teacher's background helps them navigate and adjust to changes in curricula. The length of time a teacher has worked in the field is a gauge of their

caliber and becomes crucial in affecting the academic achievement of their pupils (Akinsolu, 2019). Over the course of their careers, teachers are said to gain a significant amount of experience through both successful and poor teaching assignments. This conviction led to an extensive study of the viewpoints of educators with differing lengths of experience in the classroom (Lisa, 2018). Numerous scholars, such as Ogundare (2019), have emphasized the need of having experienced teachers in educational environments. Regarding the relationship between the educational experience and the learning results of students, these researchers have similar opinions. Most people agree that experience improves teaching abilities and that students learn best from instructors who have a wealth of teaching experience. According to Richards (2020), new teachers may find their work stressful at first, but as they gain experience, they are able to build a toolkit of teaching techniques that they can use for the rest of their careers.

Teachers' pre-existing experiences as students and teachers have an impact on their attitudes about teaching. The significance of teachers' teaching experience in relation to students' learning outcomes, as measured by their performance in SSC examinations, was revealed by the study conducted by Adeyemo's (2018), which investigated the correlation between teachers' teaching experience and students' learning outcomes in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. According to the study, schools that had a greater percentage of instructors with five years or more of experience in the classroom performed better than those where a bigger percentage of teachers had less than that amount of experience.

According to Sodaak and Podell (2017), compared to teachers with less experience, experienced teachers are typically more reluctant to adopt new activities and to

modify their ideas about self-efficacy. Onanuga (2020), on the other hand, presented the argument that longer tenure in the teaching field frequently results in lower production, making educators more prone to laziness and a lack of commitment. According to Gorrell and Dharmadasa (2014), more seasoned teachers prioritize issues with classroom management and instruction structure, stressing the importance of these aspects for students, whereas less experienced teachers tend to focus more on introducing new instructional approaches.

In contrast to their less experienced peers, science teachers with greater expertise had better mean utilization scores of innovative teaching practices, according to Anchor (2020). In a similar vein, Khurshid and Zahur (2013) found that more experienced teachers showed a stronger knowledge of and use of creative tactics than less experienced teachers. Thus, the purpose of this study was to evaluate how science teachers in a particular Nigerian location were implementing novel approaches when teaching science to senior school students. Making relevant suggestions that would improve students' performance in scientific classes was the goal.

The general objective of this study is to identify the strategies used in implementing the biology-related disciplines' curricula during the New normal era in public and private universities in Osun State, Nigeria as well as specific objectives to:

(a). identify the strategies used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during the new normal era in public and private universities in Osun State, Nigeria; and
(b). explore the online platforms employed in the implementation of selected Biology-related disciplines curricula in public and private universities in the study area
This study is focused towards significant benefits for various stakeholders, encompassing students, lecturers, universities, curriculum specialist, future

researcher, school administrators, and experts within the academic community. Furthermore, the study also examined the strategies and online platforms used in implementing selected Biology-related disciplines curricula during new normal era in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive survey research design aimed at identifying the strategies used for implementing Biology-related discipline curricula during COVID-19 era. According to Ali (2016), a survey is descriptive research that looks for or uses sample data from an investigation to record, characterize, and explain what exists or does not exist regarding the current state of the topic under study. This study focuses on individuals or objects, examining their attitudes, belief systems, opinions, and behavioral patterns, making it a crucial consideration for this study. The study focused on the following Biology-related disciplines: Microbiology, Medicine and Surgery, Anatomy, Physiology, Public health, Biology education, Nursing Science, Biochemistry, Zoology, Medical rehabilitation, Dentistry, Virology, Agricultural Science, Botany, and Community health.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to select 45 lecturers from three universities (One federal, one state, and one private) in the study area. Simple random sampling technique was to select the universities, followed by random selection of three common Biology-related departments (Anatomy, Physiology and Microbiology) from each university, resulting in nine departments. Accidental sampling was then used to select five lecturers from each department. Data collection was primarily carried out using a checklist. The Checklist for Curriculum Implementation Strategies (CCIS) was subjected to expert validation, where two lecturers from the Department of Zoology

and Botany, Faculty of Science, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife assessed its relevance, clarity, and adequacy. Their feedback led to the revisions, resulting in the final version of the instrument for data collection

To ensure the instrument's reliability, a pilot test was conducted with a separate group of respondents from the sample area. The data were then analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.84 as confirmed by Cronbach alpha tests, indicating a high level of reliability.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the strategies used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines' curricula during the new normal era in public and private universities in Osun State Nigeria?

To answer this question, frequency counts and percentages were used to assess the strategies used in implementing the curricula of Biology-related discipline during the new normal era. The decision was then made as regards being used or not. Whenever the percentages of 'seldom used' and 'not used' were higher than the percentages of 'very often used' and 'used', it was interpreted that the 'seldom used' and 'not used' categories were not used and also, whenever the percentages of 'very often used' and 'used' were higher than the percentages of 'seldom used' and 'not used' it was interpreted that 'very often used' and 'used' were the most commonly used categories. These were then subjected to descriptive analysis of frequency counts and percentage, and the results are presented in Table 4.1. The extent of each variable was independently assessed. VOU means Very Often Used, OU means Often Used, SU means Seldom Used, and NU means Not Used. The results are presented in the tables 1 and 2 and figure 2.

TABLE 1: Strategies used in implementing the curricula of Selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19

S/N	STATEMENTS	V O U	O U	S U	N U	DECISION
1	Lecturer-Lead Conversation Method	17(37.8)	9(20.0)	4(8.9)	15(33.3)	Used
2	Virtual field trip	2(4.4)	6(13.3)	10(22.2)	27(60.0)	Not used
3	Conferencing	5(11.1)	8(17.8)	11(24.4)	21(46.7)	Not used
4	Multimedia Approach	5(11.1)	9(20.0)	12(26.7)	19(42.2)	Not used
5	Peer-Lead Conversation	5(11.1)	18(40.0)	11(24.4)	11(24.4)	Used
6	Instructional Conversation	6(13.3)	7(15.6)	7(15.6)	25(55.6)	Not used
7.	Peer-Lead Instruction	4(8.9)	21(46.7)	12(26.7)	8(17.8)	Used
8	Science Text Cards	3(6.7)	10(22.2)	11(24.4)	21(46.7)	Not used
9	Flipped Classroom	1(2.2)	22(48.9)	14(31.1)	8(17.8)	Used
10	ICT Enabled Learning	5(11.1)	11(24.4)	6(13.3)	23(51.1)	Not used
11	Video Clips	7(15.6)	9(20.0)	7(15.6)	22(48.9)	Not used
12	Brainstorming	12(26.7)	19(42.2)	7(15.6)	7(15.6)	Used
13	Virtual Science Labs	4(8.9)	6(13.3)	11(24.4)	24(53.3)	Not used
14	Science Movies	3(6.7)	7(15.6)	6(13.3)	29(64.4)	Not used
15	Hand-on-Activities	3(6.7)	14(31.1)	10(22.2)	18(40.0)	Not used
16	Science Posters	5(11.1)	2(4.4)	5(11.1)	33(73.3)	Not used
17	Inquiry-Based Learning	3(6.7)	6(13.3)	6(13.3)	30(66.7)	Not used
18	App Creation	1(2.2)	8(17.8)	6(13.3)	30(66.7)	Not used
19	Lecture-Teaching Method	8(17.8)	28(62.2)	2(4.4)	7(15.6)	Used
20	Video Diaries	1(2.2)	6(13.3)	10(22.2)	28(62.2)	Not used

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES, EDUCATION AND LITERARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

21	Team-Based Learning	6(13.3)	3(6.7)	8(17.8)	28(62.2)	Not used
22	Interactive Visuals	3(6.7)	7(15.6)	5(11.1)	30(66.7)	Not used
23	Project-Based Learning	5(11.1)	4(8.9)	9(20.0)	27(60.0)	Not used
24	Interactive Video Quizzes	3(6.7)	3(6.7)	4(8.9)	35(77.8)	Not used
25	Audio and Video-taped	3(6.7)	(2.2)	6(13.3)	35(77.8)	Not used
	Protocols					
26	Problem-Based Learning	4(8.9)	6(13.3)	8(17.8)	27(60.0)	Not used
27	The Muddiest point	1(2.2)	10(22.2)	12(26.7)	22(48.9)	Not used
	Techniques					
28	Embedded Power point	5(11.1)	13(28.9)	9(20.0)	18(40.0)	Not used
29	Think pair share	3(6.7)	8(17.8)	8(17.8)	26(57.8)	Not used
30	Reciprocal Questioning	4(8.9)	15(33.3)	11(24.4)	15(33.3)	Not used
31	Audience Response tool	9(20.0)	3(6.7)	15(33.3)	18(40.0)	Not used
32	Mobile and Tablets Devices	6(13.3)	10(22.2)	13(28.9)	16(35.6)	Not used
33	Laboratory Experimentation	6(13.3)	1(2.2)	10(22.2)	28 (12.6)	Not used
34	Discovery Approach	4(8.9)	5(11.1)	6(13.3)	30(66.7)	Not used
35	Field trip/ Excursion	3(6.7)	2(4.4)	8(17.8)	32(71.1)	Not used
36	Micro Teaching	4(8.9)	13(28.9)	13(28.9)	15(33.3)	Not used
37	Individualized Instruction	4(8.9)	2(4.4)	6(13.3)	33(73.3)	Not used
38	Peer Tutoring	4(8.9)	9(20.0)	13(28.9)	19(42.2)	Not used
39	Resource Person	3(6.7)	5(11.1)	4(8.9)	33(73.3)	Not used
40	Face-to Face teaching	5(11.1)	1(2.2)	4(8.9)	35(77.8)	Not used

Source: field survey, 2023

Table 1 showed the strategies used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area. From the Table 1, Lecturer teaching Method (80.0%), Brainstorming (68.9%), Lecturer-Lead Conversation (57.8%), Peer-Lead Instruction (55.6%), Peer-Lead Conversation (51.1%), Flipped Classroom (51.1%) are the strategies used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19. However, a lot of strategies were not used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area, which include: Virtual field trip (17.7%), Conferencing (28.9%), Multimedia Approach (31.1%), Instructional Conversation (28.9%), Science Text Cards (28.9%), ICT Enabled Learning (35.5), Video Clips (36.6%), Visual Science Labs (22.2), Science Movies (22.3%), Hand-on-Activities (37.8%), Science Posters (15.5%), Inquiry-Based Learning (20.0%), App Creation (20.0%), Video Diaries (15.5), Team-Based Learning (20.0%), Interactive Visuals (22.3%), Project-Based Learning (20.0%), Interactive Video Quizzes (13.4%), Video-taped Protocols (8.9%), Problem-Based Learning (22.2%), The Muddiest point Techniques (24.4%), Embedded Power point (40.0%), Think

pair share (24.5%), Reciprocal Questioning (42.2%), Audience Response tool (26.7%), Mobile and Tablets Devices (35.6%), Laboratory Experimentation (15.5%), Discovery Approach (20.0%), Field trip/ Excursion (11.1%), Micro Teaching (37.8%), Individualized Instruction (13.3%), Peer Tutoring (28.9%), Resource Person (17.8%), and Face-to Face teaching (13.3%).

In summary, the strategies used in implementing the curricula of Biology related disciplines during the new normal era in public and private universities in Osun state includes; Lecturer teaching Method (80.0%), Brainstorming (68.9%), Lecturer-Lead Conversation (57.8%), Peer-Lead Instruction (55.6%), Peer-Lead Conversation (51.1%), Flipped Classroom (51.1%).

Furthermore, the strategies used appeared based on online, blended and those who did not use any strategy at all.

The figure 1 showed the percentages of the online strategies, blended strategies and no strategy used. Where the bar graph is the highest with (85%) shows the predominant method used while the bar chart next to the highest one with (15%) shows the second method used while the third bar chart with (0%) shows that there was no school without any strategy used to implement the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines.

TABLE 2: Summary of the methods used as teaching strategies in implementing the Curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19

Strategies	Frequency	Percent
Online	18	40.00
Blended	20	44.44
Face-to-face	7	15.56
No strategy used	0	0.0
Total	45	100.0

Figure 2: A bar chart method that were used inform of teaching strategies in implementing the curricula of Selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19

Figure 2 revealed the summary of the method used inform of teaching strategies in implementing the curricula of Selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19. From the result of the analysis of figure 2, Blended strategies (44.44%) was the predominant method used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19, while Online strategies (40.0%) was also adopted and the face-to-face strategies (15.56%) was also utilised according to the responses of the lecturers. Thus, there were no schools without any strategy to implement selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19.

Research Question 2: What online platforms are utilized in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during the new normal era in

public and private universities in the study area?

To answer this question, frequency counts and percentages were used to examine the online platforms used in implementing the curricula of Biology-related discipline during the new normal era. The decision was then made as regards being used or not. Whenever the percentages 'used' were higher than the percentages of 'not used, it was interpreted as 'used' and also, whenever the percentages of 'not used' were higher than the percentages of 'used' it was interpreted as 'not used'. These were then subjected to descriptive analysis of frequency counts and percentage, and the results are presented in Table 3. The extent of each variable was independently assessed. The results are presented in the tables 3.

TABLE 3: Online platforms used in implementing the curricula of Selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 as responded by Lecturers in the selected Universities in the study area.

ONLINE PLATFORMS		USED	NOT USED	DECISION
		F (%)	F (%)	
1	Google classroom	44(97.8)	1(2.2)	Used
2	Skype.com	23(53.3)	21(46.7)	Used
3	Canvas	43(93.3)	3(6.7)	Used
4	GoToMeeting.com	29(64.4)	16(35.6)	Used
5	Zoom(zoom.com)	28(62.2)	17(37.8)	Used
6	Vedamo.com	5(11.1)	40(88.9)	Not used
7	Blackboard.com	7(15.6)	38(84.4)	Not used
8	alison.com	28(62.2)	17(37.8)	Used
9	Udemy.com	19(42.2)	26(57.8)	Not used
10	Memory.com	42(93.3)	3(6.7)	Used
11	Google hangouts	5(11.1)	40(88.9)	Not used
12	MOOC.org	2(4.4)	43(95.6)	Not used
13	Schoology (schoology.com)	1(1.1)	44(97.8)	Not used
14	Teacherspayteacher.com	2(4.4)	43(95.6)	Not used
15	academicearth.com	1(1.1)	44(97.8)	Not used
16	Openculture.com	1(1.1)	44(97.8)	Not used
17	Edmodo (edmodo.com)	4(8.9)	41(91.1)	Not used
18	Learnopia.com	1(1.1)	44(97.8)	Not used
19	Google meet Apps	37(82.2)	8(17.8)	Used
20	Google Drive apps	36(80.0)	9(20.0)	Used
21	Cellphone/telephone calling	37(82.2)	8(17.8)	Used
22	Emails for sending materials online	38(84.4)	7(15.6)	Used
23	WhatsApp group	42(93.3)	3(6.7)	Used
24	Flipped classroom	35(77.8)	10(22.2)	Used
25	Mobile text	33(73.3)	12(26.7)	Used
26	Edx.org	6(13.3)	39(86.7)	Not used

27	Easyclass.com	7(15.6)	38(84.4)	Not used
28	Coursera.com	8(17.8)	37(82.2)	Not used
29	Lessonpaths.com	3(6.7)	42(93.3)	Not used
30	Futurelearn.com	3(6.7)	42(93.3)	Not used

Source: field survey, 2023

Table 3 showed the online platforms used in implementing the curricula of Selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area. From the Table, Google classroom (97.8%), Skype.com (53.3%), Canvas (93.3%), GoToMeeting.com (64.4%) Zoom (zoom.com) (62.2%), alison.com (62.2%), Memory.com (93.3%), Google meet Apps (82.2%), Google Drive apps (80.0%), Cellphone/telephone calling (82.2%), Emails for sending materials online (84.4%), WhatsApp group (93.3%), Flipped classroom (77.8%), Mobile text (73.3%), and futurelearn.com (6.7%) are the online platforms used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area.

Meanwhile, a number of online platforms were not being used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area. These include; Google hangouts (11.1%), MOOC.org (4.4%), Schoology (schoology.com) (1.1%), Teacherspayteacher.com (4.4%), academicearth.com (1.1%), Openculture.com (1.1%), Edmodo (edmodo.com) (8.9%), Learnopia.com (1.1%), Vedamo.com (11.1%), Blackboard.com (15.6%), Udemy.com (42.2%), edx.org (13.3%), easyclass.com (15.6%), Coursera.com (17.8%), lessonpaths.com (6.7%)

DISCUSSION

The study out to identify the strategies used in implementing the biology-related disciplines' curricula during the New normal era in public and private universities in Osun State, Nigeria. In

order to achieve this, two research questions were raised and answered.

The study sought to determine the implementation of curricula of Biology-related courses in the new post- COVID-19 era among private and public universities in Osun state, Nigeria. In order to achieve this, four research questions were raised and answered.

The findings of the study showed that, Lecturer-Lead Conversation Method, Peer-Lead Conversation, Peer-Lead Instruction, Flipped Classroom, Brainstorming, and Lecture-Teaching Method are the strategies used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19. This implies that very few strategies were used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 era among private and public universities in Osun state, Nigeria. Also, from the result of the analysis, Blended strategies were the predominant methods used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19. The findings of the study showed the online platforms used in implementing the curricula of Selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area were Google classroom, Skype.com, Whatsapp.com, GoToMeeting.com, Zoom (zoom.com), alison.com, Memory.com, Google meet Apps, Google Drive apps, Cellphone/telephone calling, Emails for sending materials online, WhatsApp group, Flipped classroom, Mobile text, and futurelearn.com. It was established from the study that the most used online platforms in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines

include; Google classroom, Whatsap.com, Memory.com and whatsapp group. However, a number of online platforms were not being used in implementing the curricula of selected Biology-related disciplines during COVID-19 in the study area, which include; Google hangouts, MOOC.org, Schoology, Teacherspayteacher.com, academicearth.com, Openculture.com, Edmodo, Learnopia.com, Vedamo.com, Blackboard.com, Udemy.com, edx.org, easyclass.com, Coursera.com, lesson paths. Similar to the result of this finding, online education has its roots in distance education and the emergence of digital technologies that facilitate the efficient and reliable delivery of lectures, virtual classroom sessions and other instructional materials and activities via the internet (Onlineeducation.com, 2020). In congruence with this, Ozturk (2019) and Soran (2020) found that teaching methods and techniques used during instruction showed that teachers are still the main authority in the class who most often lecture, direct questions to students and guide teacher centered discussions, in contrast to the student-centered preference in the curriculum.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the strategies employed in implementing the curricula revealed a shift towards blended teaching methods, including Lecturer-Lead Conversation Method, Peer-Lead Conversation, Peer-Lead Instruction, Flipped Classroom, Brainstorming, and Lecture-Teaching Method. Online platforms such as Google Classroom, Skype, WhatsApp, GoToMeeting, Zoom, and others were commonly utilized, showcasing adaptability in the face of the new normal. Ultimately, this research contributes to our understanding of how Biology-related curricula can be effectively implemented in the new normal era, and provide insights for educators, policymakers, stakeholders seeking to

optimize online learning environments for science education

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